

Irreversible Processes from Classical Mechanics?

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A hot gas at temperature T_1 placed in contact with a cooler one at T_2 is said to undergo an irreversible process (suggesting an arrow of time) in which the two gases achieve the same temperature. This is usually presented as a thermodynamics/statistical mechanics problem with the notion of entropy increasing.

On the other hand, one may consider a ball, in a Newton's cradle, strike another ball at rest. All of the momentum and energy of the first ball is transferred to the second and the first ball is now at rest. This is a reversible process, but we argue that this example shows that in a collision of a particle with momentum in one direction with another with zero or small momentum, there is a tendency, from conservation of total energy and momentum, for momentum and energy to be transferred to the second particle. As a result, some energy of the first particle is lost and there is a directional transfer (even in the reversible case). We argue that this classical mechanical result may account for the equilibration of the two gases, the irreversibility of this process and the arrow of time, without any notion of thermodynamics or entropy appearing.

Equilibration of Two Gases

If one places two gases with temperatures T_1 and T_2 , such that $T_1 > T_2$, in contact (neither being insulated) then the temperature of T_1 decreases and that of T_2 increases until both gases have the same temperature. This is a standard problem from thermodynamics. No work is done and there is no overall energy loss. Using a result from thermodynamics, namely that change in energy is $\int c_v dT$ where c_v is the same constant for both gases:

$$\int (-c_v) dT (T_1 \text{ to } T) + \int c_v dT (T_2 \text{ to } T) \text{ yields } T = .5(T_1 + T_2) \quad ((2))$$

The process is irreversible and so there is an arrow of time. These are concepts associated with thermodynamics/statistical mechanics. It is said that entropy increases and so would not spontaneously decrease in order to create the time reversed picture. We ask, however, whether these results may be explained solely from classical mechanical considerations .

Classical Mechanics and Conservation of Total Energy and Momentum

Classical mechanics suggests that collisions between particles conserve total energy and momentum. In general, such collisions are nonelastic, meaning that kinetic energy before is higher than after because energy is lost to sound, deformation etc. If one considers a Newton's cradle situation which is elastic, then a ball with momentum p strikes another identical ball transferring all of its momentum and energy. This is a reversible process, i.e. the movie of the event played backwards may also spontaneously occur.

We suggest that in this example, the main idea is the momentum is transferred from a particle with high momentum to one with none. This idea holds for both the first collision and its time reversed situation. Furthermore, it should hold for a higher momentum striking a lower one in

one dimension. If one has a gas with a high T (temperature), this means that momenta perpendicular to the interface of the two gases in the hot gas are higher than those in the gas with a lower temperature. From classical mechanics (conservation of total energy and momentum) we argue that there will be a net transfer of momentum and hence energy to the cooler gas. The particles in the cool gas collide with each other at various angles and so this energy leads to an increased temperature, while the first gas loses temperature. When the two gases have the same temperature both have the same average momentum perpendicular to the interface and there is no net transfer of momentum/energy. In such a case, there is no tendency for the time reversed picture to occur i.e. the situation is irreversible and there is an arrow of time. We argue that this follows directly from classical mechanical arguments without any notion of thermodynamics or entropy.

Entropy Considerations

Using Shannon's entropy from statistical mechanics together with the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $C \exp(-e_i/T) = p(e_i)$, entropy for each gas is:

$$S = -\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) = \text{constant } T/T + \ln(\sum_i \exp(-e_i/T)) \quad ((3))$$

Here constant T = average energy for an ideal gas.

The form $p(e_i)$ proportional to $\exp(-e_i/T)$ follows from comparing $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and $p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_3)p(e_4)$ ((3b)) i.e. taking \ln of the latter and equating to the former multiplied by $-1/T$.

In the above section we argued that a high p value tends to transfer momentum (and energy) to a lower p value i.e. there is a bias. This breaks up equilibrium, but the result $\exp(-e_i/T)$ shows that energies much higher than T have very low probability, thus high p values (equilibrium breakers) are very rare.

$$dS/dT \text{ of } ((3)) \text{ yields } dT/(TT) * E_{ave} = C_3 dT/T \quad ((4))$$

Gas 1 goes from T_1 to $.5(T_1+T_2)$ and gas 2 from T_2 to $.5(T_1+T_2)$ with $T_1 > T_2$.

Integrating ((4)) shows the change in entropy is proportional to:

$$2 \ln(.5(T_1+T_2)) - \ln(T_1) - \ln(T_2) \quad ((5))$$

((5)) is 0 if $T_1=T_2$, but what is it for T_1 and T_2 greater than 1?

One may compare:

$$T_1 T_1/4 + T_2 T_2/4 + T_1 T_2/2 \text{ versus } T_1 T_2 \quad \text{Or } T_1 T_1 + T_2 T_2 \text{ versus } 2 T_1 T_2$$

For $T_1 > T_2$, $T_2 = T_1 + b$ with $b > 0$ so $T_1 T_1 + T_2 T_2 > 2 T_1 T_2$ so the change in the absolute value of entropy is positive for the two gases equilibrating their temperatures. The concept of entropy follows from statistical mechanics, and the irreversibility and arrow of time are associated with an increase in entropy. We argue, however, that all of these results follow from the classical

mechanical conservation of energy and momentum leading to a net transfer of momentum and hence energy from the hot gas to the cold until they have the same temperature i.e. the same average momentum values perpendicular to the interface. The use of entropy is a quantitative approach to dealing with the probability balance ((3b)) for equilibrium. In equilibrium there is no net momentum transfer. Thus the classical mechanical arguments apply to a nonequilibrium situation transforming into an equilibrium one.

The Case of Friction

We try to extend the above ideas to the idea of friction. In the case of friction, one has a body which has a constraint in the form of all of its particles having the same velocity (in addition to thermal motion). This means there is net momentum in one direction and this momentum of various particles represents kinetic energy in one direction (as opposed to thermal energy). The rough surface over which the body moves (hence friction) has a temperature meaning that there is equal probability for a particle to have p or $-p$. As a result, we suggest the moving body tends to share some of its motion momentum with particles in the floor. As a result, it loses kinetic energy in one direction and slows down. The basic idea seems again to follow from classical mechanics and is defined as the tendency of a momentum in one direction to transfer partially to a particle which does not have this momentum. In this case, one deals with averages. On average, the particles in the floor do not have net momentum so we argue for a momentum transfer,

The floor has only a temperature and so this energy is distributed in order to increase the temperature. There is no net momentum in the particles in the floor and so no tendency of transferring momentum in one direction to the body. Thus the process is irreversible, but this again seems to follow from classical mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the classical mechanical ideas of conservation of total energy and momentum in a collision between two particles leads to the tendency of a particle with momentum in one direction transferring it one with a lower or no momentum in that direction (either directly or on average in the case of friction). In other words, there is a direction of flow of energy. If one has two gases, one with a high temperature and the other with a low, the first has high momentum values perpendicular to the interface and there is a tendency to have momentum and hence energy transferred to the second gas. This occurs until the second gas has the same temperature as the first and there is no net momentum advantage of the first gas. Thus this process is irreversible and there is an arrow of time. We argue, however, that it seems it may be explained directly from the classical mechanical ideas of conservation of total energy and momentum.